

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Review of Teacher's World

RESEARCH ARTICLE

OPEN ACCESS

Freely available online

Received: 11 October 2022
Accepted: 27 December 2022Corresponding author:
Amit Anand¹
Research Scholar
Faculty of Education
L.N.M University Darbhanga
India
Email:
amitanand0011@gmail.comReviewing editor:
Dr Ishrat Naaz
Assistant Professor
Galgotias University
IndiaDisclosure statement
No potential conflict of interest
was reported by the
author(s).

Citation information

Cite this article as: Anand, A. (2023). Changing Role Of Teachers In New Education Policy 2020h. Review of Teacher's World, 2(1), 19-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Changing Role Of Teachers In New Education Policy 2020

Amit Anand¹

Abstract: Education is the backbone of a nation. It paves the way for all round development including peace, progress and prosperity of a man, society and Country. With the changing scenario of Global world a more meaningful technology-based education system became the crying need of the hour. Hence National Education policy 2020 was launched by the Central Govt of India on 29th July 2020 to meet the Challenges of modern society. After a gap of nearly 34 Years NEP 2020 will now definitely prove the most effective and outstanding education policy of modern India. Only a value-based education system can bring basic changes in old education and examination system. Now multidisciplinary education system of Global Standards and National Research Foundation will be created as an apex body for fostering a strong research culture among teachers of today. More research facilities would be provided to improve their capacity and capability. This new policy provides for reforms at all levels of education form school to higher education. It focuses on -I.Early Childhood Care II.Reform the current exam system III. Strengthen teacher-training IV. Restructure the education regulatory framework. The role of Teacher is to shape the minds of the younger generation and hence teachers must be passionate, motivated and well qualified. Provisions have been made even for online learning as an alternative to regular classroom interaction between teachers and students for better understanding. Detailed provisions of New Education Policy has been well documented. The present conceptual research paper is to study the objective of New Education Policy 2020, its features and Role of Teachers. The students-teacher interaction is much significant in the new education era.

Keywords: Features of NEP, Role of Teacher, Restructure

1.1 Introduction

National Education Policy 2020 is an attempt for the successful Revival of Learning and Guru Shishay Concept prevalent in Ancient India. Long ago, our old universities like Nalanda and Takshshila- centres of Higher Learning and Knowledge- were role models for the people of the whole world. But gone are the days! Now Govt of India keeping in view a better approach to Learning- Teaching Methods, wants to adopt an uniform education policy for the whole country. After long debates and deliberations, the Central Govt contemplates an Indian - Centred Education

system that creates an equitable and vibrant knowledge society by providing a high quality education to all.

My present paper is an humble attempt to study the aim and objective of NEP 2020, its features as well as Status of Teachers in the implementation and success of the Policy. The students-teacher interaction is going to play a significant role in the upcoming new education era.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- To understand the basic elements of NEP 2020.
- To discuss the features of NEP 2020.
- To discuss the Status and Role of the Teacher in NEP 2020.
- To outline the features of New Higher Education System
- To identify the challenges of NEP 2020.

2.1 Research Methodology

This research paper has been designed for the purpose of study, and this study is an effort to present the current scenario of education system, exam system and research Practices. Govt. decision to reform the education and exam system is a milestone in this regard. The study is mainly based on the secondary data collected from different sources like reports, articles and journals.

3.1 Salient Features of NEP 2020

Right to Education Act 2009, provides for free and compulsory education to all children from the age of 06 to 14 years. NEP 2020 recommends extending the ambit of the R T E Act to include early Childhood education and Secondary school education. This would extend the coverage of the Act to all children between the ages of 03 to 18 Years.

3.2 Curriculum Framework

Curriculum Framework must be reconstructed on the basis of the development needs of students. This would consist of a 5+3+3+4 design comprising-

- Five Years of Foundational Stage (3 Years of Pre-Primary school and class I & II)
- Three Years of Preparatory Stage (Class III to V)
- Three Years of Middle Stage (Class VI to VIII)
- Four Years of Secondary Stage (Class IX to XII)

Medium of instruction and education at Foundational Stage would be mother tongue and regional languages.

3.3 School Examination Reforms

Reforms in the School Exam recommended by the NEP 2020 include tracking the progress report of the students throughout their stay in the School. Another important recommendation is the restructuring of the Board Exam to test

only core concepts, skills and higher order thinking and capacities. Semester wise Study facility would be available to students. Students will have multiple choice of subjects. Board examination would be held only at 12th level. All School Exams will be semester wise twice in a year.

3.4 Higher Education & Ph.D

There would be four-year Graduation-Course followed by one-year Post-Graduate Course under multidisciplinary Education System. Students would have complete freedom to opt subjects of his choice . Now there would be no bifurcation of Arts, Science, and Commerce education.

Students will get multiple choice of subjects. This would remove the stress and tension of students. Now there would be no M .Phil Course before Ph.D Registration. Students who are doing Graduation Course will get Certificate after completing one year. Diploma Certificate on Completing of two years and degree certificate after completing full course. There would be Credit system for graduation. For each year student will get some Credits which he or she can utilize if he/she takes break in course back again to complete course.

3.5 Research and Development

The Multidisciplinary Education and Research Universities would form the apex of the Higher Education System. Research in these institutes would be supported by a new national Research Foundation. There would be provisions for handsome amount for National Research Fund.

3.6 Status and Role of Teacher

The Role of Teacher is to shape the minds of the younger generation. Teachers must be passionate, trained, motivated and well – qualified. Students spend a great deal of time with their teacher and therefore the teacher becomes role model to them. Interaction between teachers and students matter a lot for all round development of students. Teachers must be caring, collaborative and inclusive and encouraging to excellence, empathy and equity .And for this teachers must be properly respected, valued and supported . Happy teachers and students make for excellent teaching and learning.

4. Conclusion

NEP 2020 proposes to change the name of Human Resource Department to Education Department, With this changed outlook we hope to see India marching ahead on the Educational Map of India.

References

- (i)Radha Mohan (2011). Research Methods in Education New Delhi : Neel Kamal Publications Ltd.
- (ii) MHRD – Government of India (2019) – Ministry of Human Resource Development – New Education Policy 2019 booklet.
- (iii)NCERT(2005), National Curriculum Framework 2005

Websites:

- i)www.india.gov.in/info
- ii)www.nnct.gov.in
- iii)www.ccs.university.ac.in